

A Comparative Study of Self Esteem among 10th Class and 12th Class Students

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ABSTRACT

The purpose research attempted to study the Study of Self- Esteem on Class, Gender and Area of Residence among 10th Class and 12th Class Students. Objectives- 1) To Study of Self- Esteem on Class, Gender and Area of Residence among 10th Class and 12th Class Students Hypotheses: 1) There is no significant difference between 10th Class and 12th Class Students on Self-Esteem. 2) There is no significant difference between Male and Female Students on Self- Esteem. 3) There is no significant difference between Urban and Rural Students on Self- Esteem. Methodology. Sample: For the present study 100 samples was selected from Aurangabad district (MS). A sample being 100 arts college students selected in this study, in each 50 male students (25 urban and 25 rural student) and 50 female students (25 urban and 25 rural students). Non-Probability Quota Sampling was used. Research Design: In the present study a balanced 2x2 factorial design will be used. Variables- The independent variables are Gender, Area of Residence and Dependent variables are Self- Esteem. Research Tools- Ratters Locus of control scale by Anand kumar and srivastava. Statistical Treatment: Mean, SD and 'F' values used. Conclusions- 1) No significant difference between 10th Class and 12th Class students on Self Esteem. 2) Girls Students high self- Esteem than Boys Students. 3) No significant difference between Urban and Rural Students on Self Esteem.

KEYWORDS: Gender and Area of Residence, Self Esteem.

INTRODUCTION

Self-esteem is a feeling of satisfaction that someone has in himself or herself in his or her own abilities. Thus it is an important component for us as well as for our society. It is the product of accumulated judgments about being good or bad, valuable or not. Self-esteem emphasizes an educational outcome, a possible job, and good relations with friends or with the couple partner, or a lifestyle which is consistent with our own values and personal interests. The primary underpinning of self-esteem is self-worth and self-image. However, the concept of self-esteem comprises a plurality of associated concepts because there is a multi-disciplinary approach in sociology, psychology, social care, and social psychology.

Self-esteem is a basic human need or motivation. He included self-esteem in his hierarchy of needs where it comes after physical, safety and belonging needs. According to Maslow, people will only grow and obtain self-actualization if they first fulfill their self-esteem. A self-esteem need comes after physical, safety and belonging needs.

The primary underpinning of good self-esteem is a positive self-worth. There are many people in today societies who have had that self-worth destroyed by various forms of child abuse. Although the physical scars of abuse, the outward evidence, is rarely seen by the rest of society once a child reaches adulthood, the inward scars remain and will affect

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the adult survivor of abuse and society, for the rest of their lives.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ponmozhi1, D. & S. Seetha Lakshmi, (2017) this study found that Therefore it is concluded that the 11th and 12th standard student respondent differ in their Total self-esteem. Therefore it is concluded that the female and male student respondent differ in their Total self-esteem. Therefore it is concluded that the urban and rural student respondent do not differ in their Total Self-Esteem. Vishavpreet Kaur and Gulpinder Singh, (2016) this study examine there exists no significant difference between the self-esteem of male and female senior secondary school student. Jahnabee Lahkar Boruah, (2016) this study found that Comparison of male and female students showed no significant difference in their levels of Self-esteem. Mohd Moshahid, (2017) this study found that there is no significant difference in the self-esteem of male and female prospective teachers. Hema R Bhadawkar, (2017) this study found that there is no significant difference in the Self Esteem of male and female B.Ed. students. Muhammad Faisal Farid and Mumtaz Akhtar, (2013) this study found that Gender difference was found in self-esteem of students. Urban students showed higher self-esteem than rural students. Anirudh Ramesh and Vandana Jain, (2018) this Study indicates there is no significance difference in the level of self-esteem between boys and girls pre university students. Robin. (2002), Joshi & Srivatsava (2009);

Srivastava & Agarwal, (2013), Singh, Haasan & Wani, (2017), this study found that Male adolescents were found significantly superior on self-esteem than female adolescents. Jahnabee Lahkar Boruah, (2016) this study found that Comparison of urban and rural students in their levels of Self-esteem showed a significant difference. Anirudh Ramesh and Vandana Jain, (2018) this Study indicates there is a significance difference in level of self-esteem among the students who are coming from urban and rural areas. Students from rural area have higher level self-esteem than compared to their counterpart i.e. students from urban area who comparatively low self-esteem. Srivastava & Joshi, (2014) reported that there is significant difference in terms of self-esteem among students urban and rural area.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

METHOD

Sample:

For the present study 100 samples was selected from Aurangabad district (MS). A sample being 120 students selected in this study, in each 60 10th Class students and 60 12th Class students. Non-Probability Quota Sampling was used. The subject selected in this sample will be used in the age group of 16-18 years and Ratio 1:1. Thus total sample includes as shown in the following table.

Table No.01

		Class				Total
		10 th Class		12 th Class students		
Gender		Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	
Area of Residence	Urban	15	15	15	15	60
	Rural	15	15	15	15	60
Total		30	30	30	30	120

Research Design

2 x 2 x2 Factorial research design used.

Table No.02

A					
		A1		A2	
B		B1	B2	B1	B2
C	C1	A1,B1,C1	A1,B2,C1	A2,B1,C1	A2,B2,C1
	C2	A1,B1,C2	A1,B2,C2	A2,B1,C2	A2,B2,C2

- A. Class A1- 10th Class A2- 12th Class students
- B. Gender **B1**- Boys Students **B2**- Girls Students
- C. Area of Residence **C1**- Urban Students **C2**- Rural Students

Variables under study

Table No.03

Variable	Type of variable	Sub. Variable	Name of variable
Class	Independent Variables	02	1. 10 th Class Students 2. 12 th Class Students
Gender	Independent Variables	02	1. Male Students 2. Female Students
Area of Residence	Independent Variables	02	1. Urban Students 2. Rural Students
	Dependent variables		Self Esteem

Research Tools

Self- Esteem Scale

Table No.04

Aspect	Name of the Test	Author	Developed	
Self-Esteem	Self- Esteem Scale	self –esteem scale originally developed by Eagly and revised by Robinson and shaver [1973]	Dr. R.N. Singh Dr. Ankita Srivastava	Item- 20
				Response -Namely very much ,much ,average, low and very low
				Reliability - 0.82.
				Validity - 0.89.

DATA ANALYSIS

Mean, S.D and ANOVA were College Students to analyses the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypotheses-01

➤ There is no significant difference between 10th Class and 12th Class students on Self Esteem.

Table No.05
Show the mean, SD and F value of Class of Self Esteem.

Factor	Class	Mean	SD	N	DF	F	Sign
Self Esteem	10 th Class Students	49.38	7.97	60	118	2.78	NS
	12 th Class Students	47.38	6.02	60			

Graph No. 01

Observation of the Table 05 and Graph No. 01 indicated that mean and SD values of Self Esteem obtained were 49.38 ± 7.97 by 10th Class Students and 47.38 ± 6.02 by 12th Class Students. It is observed that the calculated F value 2.78 is Low than the table value (0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels). That is to say that this hypothesis is accepted. It means that no significant difference between 10th Class and 12th Class students on Self Esteem.

Hypotheses-02

➤ There is no significant difference between Boys and Girls Students on Self Esteem.

Table No.06
Show the mean, SD and F value of Gender of Self Esteem.

Factor	Gender	Mean	SD	N	DF	F	Sign
Self Esteem	Boys Students	47.13	6.30	60	118	4.35	0.05
	Girls students	49.63	7.67	60			

Graph No. 02

Observation of the Table 06 and Graph No. 02 indicated that mean and SD values of Self Esteem obtained were 47.13 ± 6.30 by the Boys Students and 49.63 ± 7.67 by Girls Students. It is observed that the calculated F value 4.35 is High than the table value (0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels). That is to say that this hypothesis is rejected. It means that Girls Students high self-Esteem than Boys Students.

Hypotheses-03

There is no significant difference between Urban and Rural 12th Class Students on Self Esteem.

Table No.07
Show the mean, SD and F value of Area of Residence of Self Esteem.

Factor	Area of Residence	Mean	SD	N	DF	F	Sign
Self Esteem	Urban Students	47.55	6.62	60	118	1.93	NS
	Rural Students	49.21	7.51	60			

Graph No. 03

Observation of the Table 07 and Graph No. 03 indicated that mean and SD values of Self Esteem obtained were 47.55 ± 6.62 by the Urban Students and 49.21 ± 7.51 by Rural Students. It is observed that the calculated F value 1.93 is Low than the table value (0.01 = 3.94 and at 0.05 = 6.90 levels). That is to say that this hypothesis is accepted. It means that no significant difference between Urban and Rural 12th Class Students on Self Esteem.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The finding of the study is based on very sample.
2. The sample was restricted to Aurangabad district in Maharashtra.
3. The study was restricted to only students only.
4. The study was restricted students are only 16-18 years only.

CONCLUSION

1. No significant difference between 10th Class and 12th Class students on Self Esteem.
2. Girls Students high self- Esteem than Boys Students.
3. No significant difference between Urban and Rural Students on Self Esteem.

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